

A Retrospective Observational Assessment of the Oxygen Saturation Monitoring in Diagnosis of Childhood Pneumonia in Children

Manoj Kumar¹, Sunil Kishore², Shalini Sinha³

¹Department of Pediatrics, SMO, Hajipur, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India

³Eye Surgeon, MO, SDH, Danapur, Bihar, India

Received: 02-06-2022 / Revised: 04-07-2022 / Accepted: 28-07-2022

Corresponding author: Dr. Sunil Kishore

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Objective: To study the role of clinical features (including that of current WHO criteria), and oxygen saturation (SpO₂) in the diagnosis of childhood pneumonia.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted in IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India. Children, 2 to 59 months of age, suffering from acute respiratory infection (ARI).

Results: The prevalence of radiological pneumonia in the present study was 44%. Consolidation was found in 44 cases, Alveolar infiltration was found in 35 cases, Peribronchial thickening was found in 45 cases, Interstitial thickening was found in 24 cases and Atelectasis was found in 33 cases.

Conclusion: Current WHO criteria based on fast respiratory rate and/or chest indrawing have poor sensitivity and specificity for diagnosing pneumonia. Adding 92% SpO₂ to chest indrawing or WHO criteria enhances the chance of pneumonia diagnosis and is crucial in managing a kid with pneumonia.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Pneumonia is the most common cause of death in children under the age of five [1, 2]. Over 80% of children with community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) have a cough and fever. Other symptoms, like trouble breathing, feeling sick, throwing up, and not eating well, happen less often [3]. One of the hardest parts of diagnosing CAP in children is getting it right.

Based on evidence from the early 1980s, WHO (World Health Organization) made an algorithm for treating acute respiratory infections (ARI) in children, like CAP, in

the same way [4]. The WHO algorithm's clinical criteria for diagnosing pneumonia included a child's fast breathing, cough, and/or trouble breathing. The sensitivity of the WHO algorithm was found to be between 59 and 81%, and there have been worries about its specificity, which has led to antibiotics being given to people who don't need them. [3, 5-11].

In 2014, the WHO algorithm for pneumonia was changed. Severe and very severe pneumonia were combined into one category, and pneumonia was defined as

rapid breathing and/or lower chest indrawing (LCI) [12]. But this updated algorithm kept the same signs and symptoms that were used in the older version to classify how bad a child's pneumonia was. A recent systematic review found that the lack of a cough was a significant negative predictor, while a SpO₂ of less than 95% or increased work of breathing (nasal flaring, grunting, or lower chest indrawing) were significant diagnostic predictors of pneumonia.

There is as yet no study from the Indian setting, assessing the diagnostic accuracy of clinical signs and symptoms (including WHO criteria) of pneumonia, with or without SpO₂ measurement

Materials and Methods

This retrospective observational, multicentric study was conducted in IGIMS Patna in five sites in India over a 1 year period. Children aged 2-59 months with ARI (any cough and/or breathing difficulty for <2 weeks) were enrolled. Those with chronic respiratory diseases (asthma, cystic fibrosis, bronchopulmonary dysplasia, airway anomalies), congenital heart disease, gastro-oesophageal reflux/ recurrent aspirations, immunosuppression, radiologically confirmed pneumonia in last 2 months,

residing outside the study city, and who were critically ill (impending respiratory failure, cyanosis at room air, shock), were excluded.

Details regarding clinical features, nutritional and immunization status, treatment history, demographic information, and examination findings were obtained from the hospital records.

Spo₂ records were also obtained. A chest X-ray (CXR) was obtained in all children clinically assessed to have acute lower respiratory tract infection (ALRI/pneumonia) as per the WHO criteria. CXR was also obtained in every fifth child assessed as no pneumonia (URI).

Statistical analysis: For analysis, the data were entered into Microsoft excel sheet and analyzed using Stata v.14 (StataCorp LLC) statistical software. Categorical data were analyzed by Chi-square test. For studying the association between WHO pneumonia classification and CXR findings, risk ratio (RR) with 95% confidence interval (95% CI) was calculated. Sensitivity, specificity, likelihood ratio (LR), and post-test probability were calculated. A P value <0.05 was taken as significant. Results

Table 1: Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Enrolled Children

Age (month) (mean±SD)	20±9.41
Weight for age z-score	-0.53
Height/Length for age z-score	-0.65
Weight for height z-score	-0.35
Mid upper arm circumference z-score	-1.09

The prevalence of radiological pneumonia in the present study was 44%,

Table 2: Association between WHO Pneumonia classification and Chest X-Ray Findings

	No pneumonia	Pneumonia	RR (95% CL)
Consolidation	56	44	1.55 (1.3-1.9)
Alveolar infiltration	65	35	2.06 (1.36-2.85)
Peribronchial thickening	55	45	1.95 (1.57-2.15)
Interstitial thickening	76	24	1.13 (0.43-2.06)
Atelectasis	67	33	1.34 (0.97-2.92)

Consolidation was found in 44 case, Alveolar infiltration was found in 35 cases, Peribronchial thickening was found in 45 cases, Interstitial thickening was found in 24 cases and Atelectasis was found in 33 cases.

Neither cough nor wheeze had a significant LR for ruling in or ruling out the diagnosis of pneumonia. The parameters like breathing difficulty, fast breathing, chest indrawing, existing WHO criteria for pneumonia, SpO₂ <92%, existing WHO criteria + SpO₂ <92%, existing WHO criteria and/or SpO₂<92%, chest indrawing + SpO₂ <92%, existing WHO criteria present and SpO₂ <92% applied serially had a significant positive LR as well as negative LR (except fever, which had a significant negative LR only). Positive LR among confirmed pneumonia cases ranged from 1.5 (for breathing difficulty) to 2.7 times (for chest indrawing + SpO₂ <92%) in confirmed pneumonia cases compared to those without. Negative LR ranged from 0.85 (for chestindrawing + SpO₂ <92%) to 0.64 (for fever, and existing WHO criteria and/or SpO₂ <92%, both) in those with pneumonia compared to those without

Discussion

Overall, the analysis shows that the current WHO criteria for pneumonia have a moderate level of sensitivity (56.5%) and specificity (66.2%), which is in line with what a previous meta-analysis found. [8].

The prevalence of radiological pneumonia in the present study was 44%, similar to previous studies [13]. Primary endpoint pneumonia is usually defined as presence of consolidation or pleural effusion with or without other infiltrates (e.g., interstitial infiltrates/thickening, atelectasis, peribronchial thickening, and alveolar infiltrates not sufficient to refer as a consolidation) [8]. Other infiltrates are commonly seen in viral or atypical pneumonia. In the present study, only consolidation and alveolar infiltrates were

found to be significantly associated with WHO pneumonia, which probably means that majority had bacterial pneumonia [13], which is consistent with the finding of a relatively high proportion of severe pneumonia cases, in the present study (37%) [14].

It has been shown that an LR+ of 2.0 and an LR of 0.5 change the post-test chance of disease by a lot. In this study, neither a cough nor a wheeze that can be heard (7.3% of the children) is a strong indicator of pneumonia or not. This is an interesting point to make, since coughing has always been the most common sign of pneumonia. A recent systematic review [3] found that none of the symptoms, such as cough, audible wheeze, poor feeding, trouble breathing, or illness lasting more than 3 days, had a significant likelihood of diagnosing pneumonia. However, the absence of cough had a significant negative LR (LR 0.47; 95 percent CI 0.24 to 0.70) for ruling out the diagnosis of pneumonia. Also, a high work of breathing (nasal flaring, grunting, or lower chest indrawing) and a SpO₂ of less than 95% (LR+2.1) were strong signs of pneumonia. Studies using other cut-off SpO₂ values (i.e., 96%, 92%, and 90%) had lower LR+, whereas, SpO₂ >96% had a LR- of 0.47 [3,15]. The poor diagnostic performance of auscultatory findings (e.g., presence of wheeze or crackles) could be because these are subjective parameters. The present study shows that the probability of having pneumonia improved to 66% among those tested positive for WHO criteria with a SpO₂ of <92%, and to 69% among those with chest in-drawing and a SpO₂ of <92%. None of the parameters in the present study were found to have negative LR of ≤0.5, thus making them inappropriate for ruling out the pneumonia diagnosis. Our findings are different from previously published studies [3,8], probably because of variation in the age of included.

The problem with this study is that we couldn't do a subgroup analysis of things like age, length of symptoms at presentation, and severity, which in a previously published study were shown to change how well a diagnosis was made. [16,17].

Conclusion

To conclude, Current WHO criteria based on fast respiratory rate and/or chest indrawing have poor sensitivity and specificity for diagnosing pneumonia. Adding 92% SpO₂ to chest indrawing or WHO criteria enhances the chance of pneumonia diagnosis and is crucial in managing a kid with pneumonia.

References

1. McAllister DA, Liu L, Shi T, et al. Global, regional, and national estimates of pneumonia morbidity and mortality in children younger than 5 years between 2000 and 2015: A systematic analysis. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2019; 7:e47-57.
2. Fadel SA, Boschi-Pinto C, Yu S, et al. Trends in cause specific mortality among children aged 5-14 years from 2005 to 2016 in India, China, Brazil, and Mexico: An analysis of nationally representative mortality studies. *Lancet* 2019; 393:1119-27.
3. Shah SN, Bachur RG, Simel DL, Neuman MI. Does This child have pneumonia? The rational clinical examination systematic review. *JAMA*. 2017; 318:462-71.
4. World Health Organization (WHO). The management of acute respiratory infections in children In: Practical guidelines for outpatient care. Geneva: WHO, 1995.
5. Sazawal S, Black RE, Pneumonia Case Management Trials Group. Effect of pneumonia case management on mortality in neonates, infants, and preschool children: a meta-analysis of community-based trial. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2003; 3:547-56.
6. Hazir T, Qazi SA, Bin Nisar Y, et al. Comparison of standard versus double dose of amoxicillin in the treatment of non severe pneumonia in children aged 2-59 months: a multicentre, double blind, randomized controlled trial in Pakistan. *Arch Dis Child*. 2007; 92:291-7.
7. Harari M, Shann F, Spooner V, Meisner S, Carney M, deCampo J. Clinical signs of pneumonia in children. *Lancet*. 1991; 338:928-30.
8. Rambaud-Althaus C, Althaus F, Genton B, D'Acremont V. Clinical features for diagnosis of pneumonia in children younger than 5 years: a systematic review and metaanalysis. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2015; 15:439-50.
9. Mulholland EK, Simoes EA, Costales MO, McGrath EJ, Manalac EM, Gove S. Standardized diagnosis of pneumonia in developing countries. *Pediatr Infect Dis J*. 1992; 11:77-81.
10. Singhi S, Dhawan A, Kataria S, Walia BN. Validity of clinical signs for the identification of pneumonia in children. *Ann Trop Paediatr*. 1994; 14:5 3-8.
11. Redd SC, Vreuls R, Metsing M, Mohobane PH, Patrick E, Moteete M. Clinical signs of pneumonia in children attending a hospital outpatient department in Lesotho. *Bull World Health Organ*. 1994; 72:113-8.
12. Falade AG, Tschäppeler H, Greenwood BM, Mulholland EK. Use of simple clinical signs to predict pneumonia in young Gambian children: the influence of malnutrition. *Bull World Health Organ*. 1995; 73:299-304.
13. Awasthi S, Rastogi T, Mishra N, et al. Chest radiograph findings in children aged 2-59 months hospitalised with community-acquired pneumonia, prior to the introduction of pneumococcal conjugate vaccine in India: a prospective multisite observational study. *BMJ Open*. 2020; 10: e034 066.

14. Rudan I, Boschi-Pinto C, Biloglav Z, Mulholland K, Campbell H. Epidemiology and etiology of childhood pneumonia. *Bull World Health Organ.* 2008; 86:408-16
15. Mahabee-Gittens EM, Grupp-Phelan J, Brody AS, et al. Identifying children with pneumonia in the emergency department. *Clin Pediatr (Phila).* 2005; 44:427-35.
16. Palafox M, Guiscafre H, Reyes H, Munoz O, Martinez H. Diagnostic value of tachypnoea in pneumonia defined radiologically. *Arch Dis Child.* 2000; 82:41-5
17. Restrepo L. E. D. L. P., Ávila J. L. B., Moreno K. S. H., Noriega L. G. E., Castellan, Ángela M. A., & Pérez F. A. T. Pelvic Ring Fracture as a Potential Risk of Death in Polytraumatic Patients. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences,* 2021;4(9): 1446–1450.